

On the Energy Efficiency of Limited-Backhaul Cell-Free Massive MIMO

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Abstract—We investigate the energy efficiency performance of cell-free Massive multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO), where the access points (APs) are connected to a central processing unit (CPU) via limited-capacity links. Thanks to the distributed maximum ratio combining (MRC) weighting at the APs, we propose that only the quantized version of the weighted signals are sent back to the CPU. Considering the effects of channel estimation errors and using the Bussgang theorem to model the quantization errors, an energy efficiency maximization problem is formulated with per-user power and backhaul capacity constraints as well as with throughput requirement constraints. To handle this non-convex optimization problem, we decompose the original problem into two sub-problems and exploit a successive convex approximation (SCA) to solve original energy efficiency maximization problem. Numerical results confirm the superiority of the proposed optimization scheme.

I. INTRODUCTION

One of the main issues for cell-free Massive multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) systems is the limited capacity of the links from the access points (APs) to the central processing unit (CPU). Following [1]–[6], we refer to these links as *backhaul links*. We study the case when only the quantized version of the weighted signal is available at the CPU and the CPU employs maximum ratio combining (MRC) detection. In [7]–[11], the authors show that exploiting optimal uniform quantization and wireless microwave links with capacity 100 Mbits/s, the performance of limited-backhaul cell-free Massive MIMO system closely approaches the performance of cell-free Massive MIMO with perfect backhaul links. We consider the energy efficiency maximization problem, where to tackle the non-convexity of the optimization problem, we decouple the original problem into two sub-problems, namely, receiver filter coefficient design, and power allocation. We next show that the receiver filter coefficient design problem can be solved through a generalized eigenvalue problem [12]–[18]. Unfortunately, the user power allocation problem is a non-convex problem, and a successive convex approximation (SCA) is used to convert the original power allocation problem into a geometric programming (GP) problem. This scheme introduces an efficient solution for the original problem [19], [20]. The contributions of the paper are summarized as follows:

1. A closed-form expression for the energy efficiency is derived, where we exploit the Bussgang decomposition

to model the effect of quantization, and present the analytical solution to find the optimal step-size of the quantizer. An expression for uplink energy efficiency is derived based on channel statistics and taking into account the effects of channel estimation errors, the effect of pilot sequences, and quantization error.

2. We decompose the non-convex original problem into two sub-problems and an iterative algorithm is developed to determine the optimal solution. An SCA is used to efficiently solve the power allocation problem. Numerical results demonstrate that the proposed scheme substantially outperforms the case with equal power allocation.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

We consider uplink transmission in a cell-free Massive MIMO system with M APs and K randomly distributed single-antenna users in a large area. Moreover, we assume each AP has N antennas. The channel coefficients between the k th user and the m th AP, $\mathbf{g}_{mk} \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times 1}$, is modeled as $\mathbf{g}_{mk} = \sqrt{\beta_{mk}} \mathbf{h}_{mk}$, where β_{mk} denotes the large-scale fading and the elements of \mathbf{h}_{mk} are independent and identically distributed (i.i.d.) $\mathcal{CN}(0, 1)$ random variables, and represent the small-scale fading [1]. All pilot sequences transmitted by the K users in the channel estimation phase are collected in a matrix $\Phi \in \mathbb{C}^{\tau_p \times K}$, where τ_p is the length of the pilot sequence (in symbols) for each user and the k th column of Φ , ϕ_k , represents the pilot sequence used for the k th user. After performing a de-spreading operation, the minimum mean square error (MMSE) estimate of the channel coefficient between the k th user and the m th AP is given by [1]

$$\hat{\mathbf{g}}_{mk} = c_{mk} \left(\sqrt{\tau_p p_p} \mathbf{g}_{mk} + \sqrt{\tau_p p_p} \sum_{k' \neq k}^K \mathbf{g}_{mk'} \phi_{k'}^H \phi_k + \mathbf{W}_{p,m} \phi_k \right), \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{W}_{p,m}$ denotes the noise sequence at the m th antenna whose elements are independent and identically distributed (i.i.d) $\mathcal{CN}(0, 1)$, p_p represents the normalized signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) of each pilot symbol (which we define in Section VI), and c_{mk} is given by $c_{mk} = \frac{\sqrt{\tau_p p_p} \beta_{mk}}{\tau_p p_p \sum_{k'=1}^K \beta_{mk'} |\phi_k^H \phi_{k'}|^2 + 1}$. The investigation of cell-free Massive MIMO with realistic COST channel model [21]–[23] will be considered in our future work.

A. Uplink Transmission

The transmitted signal from the k th user is represented by $x_k = \sqrt{q_k} s_k$, where s_k ($\mathbb{E}\{|s_k|^2\} = 1$) and q_k denotes the

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transmitted symbol and the transmit power from the k th user, respectively. The received signal at the m th AP is given by

$$\mathbf{y}_m = \sqrt{\rho} \sum_{k=1}^K \mathbf{g}_{mk} \sqrt{q_k} s_k + \mathbf{n}_m, \quad (2)$$

where each element of $\mathbf{n}_m \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times 1}$, $n_{n,m} \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, 1)$ is the noise at the m th AP, and ρ is the normalized uplink SNR.

B. Optimal Uniform Quantization Model

The Bussgang theorem [24] is exploited, where a nonlinear output of a quantizer can be introduced by a linear function plus uncorrelated distortion as $Q(z) = az + n_d$, $\forall k$, where a is a constant, n_d refers to the distortion noise, z is the input of the quantizer [8], [9], [24]. The term a is given by $a = \frac{\mathbb{E}\{zh(z)\}}{\mathbb{E}\{z^2\}} = \frac{1}{p_z} \int_{\mathcal{Z}} zh(z) f_z(z) dz$, where $p_z = \mathbb{E}\{|z|^2\} = \mathbb{E}\{z^2\}$ denotes the power of z and we drop absolute value as z is a real number, and $f_z(z)$ represents the probability distribution function of z . We define the second parameter $b = \frac{\mathbb{E}\{h^2(z)\}}{\mathbb{E}\{z^2\}} = \frac{1}{p_z} \int_{\mathcal{Z}} h^2(z) f_z(z) dz$ [8], [9], [24]. We aim to maximize the signal-to-distortion noise ratio (SDNR), which is defined as follows: $\text{SDNR} = \frac{\mathbb{E}\{(az)^2\}}{\mathbb{E}\{n_d^2\}} = \frac{a^2}{b-a^2}$, where $\mathbb{E}\{az^2\} = a^2 p_z$, and $\mathbb{E}\{n_d^2\} = p_{n_d} = (b-a^2)p_z$. In practice, we divide the input by its standard deviation, and multiply the output by the same factor. By introducing a new variable $\tilde{z} = \frac{z}{\sqrt{p_z}}$, we have

$$Q(z) = \sqrt{p_z} Q(\tilde{z}) = \tilde{a} \sqrt{p_z} \tilde{z} + \sqrt{p_z} \tilde{n}_d = \tilde{a} z + \sqrt{p_z} \tilde{n}_d. \quad (3)$$

The optimal step-size of the quantizer, Δ_{opt} , can be obtained by solving the following maximization problem: $\Delta_{\text{opt}} = \arg \max_{\Delta} \text{SDNR}$. In [8], [9], by deriving closed-form expressions for a and b , we numerically solve this maximization problem, and the resulting distortion power are summarized in Table I, where α refers to the number of quantization bits.

C. The Signal Received at the CPU

At each AP, MRC weighting is performed. Using Bussgang's theorem [24], a nonlinear output can be represented as a linear function as follows: $Q(\mathcal{R}(\hat{\mathbf{g}}_{mk}^H \mathbf{y}_m)) = \tilde{a} \mathcal{R}(\hat{\mathbf{g}}_{mk}^H \mathbf{y}_m) + \sigma_{\mathcal{R}(\hat{\mathbf{g}}_{mk}^H \mathbf{y}_m)} \tilde{n}_{d,mk}$, $\forall k$, where $\sigma_{\mathcal{R}(\hat{\mathbf{g}}_{mk}^H \mathbf{y}_m)}$ is the standard deviation of the $\mathcal{R}(\hat{\mathbf{g}}_{mk}^H \mathbf{y}_m)$, where \mathcal{R} represents the real part of a complex number. Note that as mentioned in the previous subsection, we use the scheme in [9] to exploit Bussgang decomposition. Here, given the fact that the input of quantizer, i.e., $\hat{\mathbf{g}}_{mk}^H \mathbf{y}_m$, is the summation of many terms, it can be approximated as a Gaussian random variable. This enables us to exploit the values given in Table I, which are obtained for Gaussian input. Note that $\sigma_{\mathcal{R}(\hat{\mathbf{g}}_{mk}^H \mathbf{y}_m)}^2 = \sigma_{\mathcal{I}(\hat{\mathbf{g}}_{mk}^H \mathbf{y}_m)}^2 = \frac{1}{2} \sigma_{\hat{\mathbf{g}}_{mk}^H \mathbf{y}_m}^2$. To improve the performance, the signal is further multiplied by the receiver filter coefficients u_{mk} , $\forall m, k$ at the CPU. The received signal at the CPU can be written as

$$r_k = \sum_{m=1}^M u_{mk} Q(\hat{\mathbf{g}}_{mk}^H \mathbf{y}_m) = \sum_{m=1}^M u_{mk} (a \hat{\mathbf{g}}_{mk}^H \mathbf{y}_m + n_{d,mk}). \quad (4)$$

We define $\mathbf{u}_k = [u_{1k}, u_{2k}, \dots, u_{Mk}]^T$ without loss of generality, it is assumed that $\|\mathbf{u}_k\| = 1$.

Table I
THE DISTORTION POWER OF A UNIFORM QUANTIZER WITH BUSSGANG DECOMPOSITION, [8], [9].

α	Δ_{opt}	$p_{\tilde{n}_d} = b - \tilde{a}^2 = \sigma_{\tilde{e}}^2$	\tilde{a}
1	1.596	0.2313	0.6366
2	0.9957	0.10472	0.88115
3	0.586	0.036037	0.96256
4	0.3352	0.011409	0.98845
5	0.1881	0.003482	0.996505
6	0.1041	0.0010389	0.99896
7	0.0568	0.0003042	0.99969

III. PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS

The aggregate received signal at the CPU can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} r_k &= \tilde{a} \sqrt{\rho} \mathbb{E} \left\{ \underbrace{\sum_{m=1}^M u_{mk} \hat{\mathbf{g}}_{mk}^H \mathbf{g}_{mk} \sqrt{q_k}}_{\text{DS}_k} \right\} s_k \\ &+ \tilde{a} \sqrt{\rho} \left(\underbrace{\sum_{m=1}^M u_{mk} \hat{\mathbf{g}}_{mk}^H \mathbf{g}_{mk} \sqrt{q_k} - \mathbb{E} \left\{ \sum_{m=1}^M u_{mk} \hat{\mathbf{g}}_{mk}^H \mathbf{g}_{mk} \sqrt{q_k} \right\}}_{\text{BU}_k} \right) s_k + \tilde{a} \sum_{k' \neq k}^K \\ &\underbrace{\sqrt{\rho} \sum_{m=1}^M u_{mk} \hat{\mathbf{g}}_{mk}^H \mathbf{g}_{mk'} \sqrt{q_{k'}} s_{k'}}_{\text{IUI}_{kk'}} + \underbrace{\tilde{a} \sum_{m=1}^M u_{mk} \hat{\mathbf{g}}_{mk}^H \mathbf{n}_m}_{\text{TN}_k} + \underbrace{\sum_{m=1}^M u_{mk} n_{d,mk}}_{\text{TQE}_k}, \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where DS_k and BU_k denote the desired signal (DS) and beamforming uncertainty (BU) for the k th user, respectively, and IUI_k represents the inter-user-interference (IUI) caused by the k' th user. In addition, TN_k accounts for the total noise (TN), and finally TQE_k refers to the total quantization error (TQE) at the k th user. The elements of quantization error are i.i.d. random variables [25]. We exploit a symmetrical quantizer, where the quantization noise has zero mean, if the probability density function of the input of the quantizer is even [26].

Proposition 1. Using Bussgang decomposition the elements of the quantization error are uncorrelated with the input of the quantizer [24], i.e., $\mathbb{E} \left\{ \left(\hat{\mathbf{g}}_{mk}^H \mathbf{y}_m \right)^H n_{d,mk} \right\} = 0$.

Hence, exploiting the analysis in [1], it can be shown that terms $\text{DS}_k \cdot s_k$, $\text{BU}_k \cdot s_k$, $\text{IUI}_{kk'} \cdot s_{k'}$, TN_k and TQE_k are mutually uncorrelated. Using the worst-case Gaussian noise, and the analysis in [1], the corresponding signal-to-interference-plus-noise ratio (SINR) is

$$\text{SINR}_k = \frac{|\text{DS}_k|^2}{\mathbb{E}\{|\text{BU}_k|^2\} + \sum_{k' \neq k}^K \mathbb{E}\{|\text{IUI}_{kk'}|^2\} + \mathbb{E}\{|\text{TN}_k|^2\} + \frac{1}{\tilde{a}^2} \mathbb{E}\{|\text{TQE}_k|^2\}} \quad (6)$$

Theorem 1. The spectral efficiency of the k th user is given by (7) (defined at the top of this page), where τ_c denotes the number of samples for each coherence interval, and

$$\mathbf{\Gamma}_k = [\gamma_{1k}, \gamma_{2k}, \dots, \gamma_{Mk}]^T, \quad (8a)$$

$$\mathbf{D}_{kk'} = \text{diag} \left[\beta_{1k'} \left(\frac{\sigma_{\tilde{e}}^2}{\tilde{a}^2} (2\beta_{1k} - \gamma_{1k}) + \gamma_{1k} \right), \dots, \right. \quad (8b)$$

$$\left. \beta_{Mk'} \left(\frac{\sigma_{\tilde{e}}^2}{\tilde{a}^2} (2\beta_{Mk} - \gamma_{Mk}) + \gamma_{Mk} \right) \right],$$

$$\mathbf{\Delta}_{kk'} = \left[\frac{\gamma_{1k} \beta_{1k'}}{\beta_{1k}}, \frac{\gamma_{2k} \beta_{2k'}}{\beta_{2k}}, \dots, \frac{\gamma_{Mk} \beta_{Mk'}}{\beta_{Mk}} \right]^T, \quad (8c)$$

$$\mathbf{R}_k = \text{diag} \left[\left(\frac{\sigma_{\tilde{e}}^2}{\tilde{a}^2} + 1 \right) \gamma_{1k}, \dots, \left(\frac{\sigma_{\tilde{e}}^2}{\tilde{a}^2} + 1 \right) \gamma_{Mk} \right], \quad (8d)$$

$$S_k(q_k, \mathbf{u}_k, b) \approx \left(1 - \frac{\tau_p}{\tau_c}\right) \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{N^2 \mathbf{u}_k^H \left(q_k \mathbf{\Gamma}_k \mathbf{\Gamma}_k^H \right) \mathbf{u}_k}{\mathbf{u}_k^H \left(N^2 \sum_{k' \neq k}^K q_{k'} |\phi_k^H \phi_{k'}|^2 \Delta_{kk'} \Delta_{kk'}^H + N \sum_{k'=1}^K q_{k'} \mathbf{D}_{kk'} + \frac{N}{\rho} \mathbf{R}_k \right) \mathbf{u}_k} \right), \text{ (bit/s/Hz)} \quad (7)$$

where $\gamma_{mk} = \sqrt{\tau_p} \beta_{mk} c_{mk}$, and $\text{diag}[\mathbf{x}]$ refers to a diagonal matrix whose diagonal elements are the elements of vector \mathbf{x} .

Proof: Please refer to Appendix A. ■

IV. TOTAL ENERGY EFFICIENCY MODEL

The total power consumption can be defined as follows [27]:

$$P_{\text{total}} = P_{\text{TX}} + P_{\text{CP}}, \quad (9)$$

where P_{TX} is the uplink power amplifiers (PAs), and P_{CP} refers to the circuit power (CP) consumption. The power consumption P_{TX} is given by $P_{\text{TX}} = \frac{1}{\zeta} \rho N_0 \sum_{k=1}^K q_k$, where ζ is the PA efficiency at each user. The power consumption P_{CP} is obtained as $P_{\text{CP}} = M P_{\text{fix}} + K P_U + \sum_{m=1}^M P_{\text{bh},m}$, where P_{fix} is a fixed power consumption at each AP, P_U denotes the required power to run circuit components at each user, and backhaul power consumption from the m th AP to the CPU is obtained as follows [28]–[30]:

$$P_{\text{bh},m} = P_{\text{BT}} \frac{R_{\text{bh},m}}{C_{\text{bh},m}}, \quad (10)$$

where P_{BT} is the total power required for backhaul traffic (BT) at full capacity, $C_{\text{bh},m}$ is the capacity of the backhaul link between the m th AP and the CPU, $R_{\text{bh},m}$ is the actual backhaul rate between the m th AP and the CPU given by

$$R_{\text{bh},m} = \frac{2 K \tau_f \alpha_m}{T_c}, \quad (11)$$

where α_m denotes the number of quantization bits at the m th APs. Note that considering the same number of bits at all APs, we drop the index m and use α as the number of quantization bits. Moreover, τ_f introduces the length of frame (which represents the length of the uplink data, in symbols) and is given by $\tau_f = \tau_c - \tau_p$. Hence, the total energy efficiency is given by

$$E_e(q_k, \mathbf{u}_k, \alpha) = \frac{B S(q_k, \mathbf{u}_k, \alpha)}{P_{\text{total}}} \text{ (bit/Joule)}, \quad (12)$$

where B is the bandwidth.

V. ENERGY EFFICIENCY MAXIMIZATION SCHEME

The total energy efficiency maximization is modelled by

$$P_1 : \max_{q_k, \mathbf{u}_k, \alpha} E_e(q_k, \mathbf{u}_k, \alpha), \quad (13a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } S_k(q_k, \mathbf{u}_k, \alpha) \geq S_k^{(r)}, \forall k, 0 \leq q_k \leq p_{\text{max}}^{(k)}, \forall k, \quad (13b)$$

$$R_{\text{bh},m} \leq C_{\text{bh}}, \quad \forall m, \quad (13c)$$

where $S_k^{(r)}$ is the required spectral efficiency of the k th user, $p_{\text{max}}^{(k)}$ and $C_{\text{bh},m}$ refer to the maximum transmit power available at user k and the capacity of backhaul link between the m th AP and the CPU, respectively. Assuming the same amount of backhaul capacity between all APs and the CPU, we drop the index m , and use C_{bh} for simplicity. Problem P_1 contains one discrete variable (the number of quantization bits). Hence, we can formulate the problem for fixed values of the number of

quantization bits α , and we investigate the optimal values of α , in numerical results. As a result, for a given α , the total energy efficiency maximization problem can be re-formulated as follows:

$$P_2 : \max_{q_k, \mathbf{u}_k} \frac{B \cdot S(q_k, \mathbf{u}_k, \alpha)}{\frac{1}{\zeta} \rho_d N_0 \sum_{k=1}^K q_k + M P_{\text{fix}} + K P_U + P_{\text{BT}} \frac{2 K \tau_f \alpha P_{\text{BT}}}{T_c C_{\text{bh}}}}, \quad (14a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } S_k(q_k, \mathbf{u}_k, \alpha) \geq S_k^{(r)}, \quad \forall k, \quad (14b)$$

$$0 \leq q_k \leq p_{\text{max}}^{(k)}, \quad \forall k. \quad (14c)$$

We reformulate Problem P_2 into the following:

$$P_3 : \quad (15a)$$

$$\max_{q_k, \mathbf{u}_k, \nu} \frac{B \cdot S(q_k, \mathbf{u}_k, \alpha)}{\frac{1}{\zeta} \rho_d N_0 \nu \sum_{k=1}^K p_{\text{max}}^{(k)} + M P_{\text{fix}} + K P_U + P_{\text{BT}} \frac{2 K \tau_f \alpha P_{\text{BT}}}{T_c C_{\text{bh}}}}, \quad (15b)$$

$$\text{s.t. } S_k(q_k, \mathbf{u}_k, \alpha) \geq S_k^{(r)}, \quad \forall k, \quad (15b)$$

$$0 \leq q_k \leq p_{\text{max}}^{(k)}, \forall k, \quad \sum_{k=1}^K q_k \leq \nu \sum_{k=1}^K p_{\text{max}}^{(k)}, \quad \nu^* \leq \nu \leq 1, \quad (15c)$$

where ν is a auxiliary variable. Moreover, based on the analysis in [19], [31], the slack variable ν^* is obtained by solving a power minimization problem subject to the same per-user power constraints in (14c) and throughput requirements in (14b). Assuming a total transmit power as $\sum_{k=1}^K q_k$, based on [19], [31], the power minimization problem (PMP) can be defined as follows:

$$P_{\text{PMP}} : \min_{q_k} \sum_{k=1}^K q_k \quad (16a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } S_k(q_k, \mathbf{u}_k, \alpha) \geq S_k^{(r)}, \quad \forall k, \quad \& \quad 0 \leq q_k \leq p_{\text{max}}^{(k)}, \forall k. \quad (16b)$$

Problem P_{PMP} is a GP and can be efficiently solved. After solving Problem P_{PMP} and finding the optimal solution q_k^+ , $\forall k$, the slack variable ν^* is obtained as $\nu^* = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^K p_{\text{max}}^{(k)}}{\sum_{k=1}^K q_k^+}$.

Theorem 2. *Optimal solution of Problems P_2 and P_3 are equal.*

Proof: Let us assume $\{\mathbf{U}^{\text{opt}}, \mathbf{q}^{\text{opt}}\}$ and $\{\tilde{\mathbf{U}}^{\text{opt}}, \tilde{\mathbf{q}}^{\text{opt}}, \tilde{\nu}\}$ are the optimal solution of Problems P_2 and P_3 , respectively. It is easy to show that $\sum_{k=1}^K \tilde{q}_k = \tilde{\nu} \sum_{k=1}^K p_{\text{max}}^{(k)}$. Moreover, based on [19, Theorem 1], $\tilde{\mathbf{U}}^{\text{opt}}$ and $\tilde{\mathbf{q}}^{\text{opt}}$ provide a feasible solution to Problem P_2 . Exploiting the per-user power constraints, using $\nu = \frac{1}{\sum_{k=1}^K p_{\text{max}}^{(k)}} \sum_{k=1}^K q_k$ and $0 \leq \nu \leq 1$, and by considering the throughput requirements, one can conclude that $\{\mathbf{U}^{\text{opt}}, \mathbf{q}^{\text{opt}}\}$ provide a feasible solution to Problem P_3 . ■

Hence, we can convert the original total energy efficiency maximization problem into a throughput maximization problem with the new total power constraint. Next, Problem P_3 is iteratively solved by performing a one-dimensional search over the variable $\nu^* \leq \nu \leq 1$ [19]. Note that for a given ν , the denominator of the objective function of Problem P_3 is a constant. Therefore, we reformulate Problem P_3 as follows:

$$P_4 : \max_{q_k, \mathbf{u}_k} S(q_k, \mathbf{u}_k, \alpha), \quad (17a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } S_k(q_k, \mathbf{u}_k, \alpha) \geq S_k^{(r)}, \forall k, 0 \leq q_k \leq p_{\max}^{(k)}, \forall k, \quad (17b)$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^K q_k \leq \nu \sum_{k=1}^K p_{\max}^{(k)}. \quad (17c)$$

Problem P_4 is not jointly convex in terms of \mathbf{u}_k and power allocation q_k , $\forall k$. To tackle this non-convexity issue, we decouple Problem P_5 into two sub-problems: receiver filter coefficient design (i.e. \mathbf{u}_k) and the power allocation problem. The optimal solution for Problem P_4 , is obtained through alternately solving these sub-problems, as explained in the following subsections.

A. Receiver Filter Coefficient Design

We solve the total energy efficiency maximization problem for a given set of power allocations at all users, $q_k, \forall k$, and fixed α . These coefficients (i.e., $\mathbf{u}_k, \forall k$) are obtained by independently maximizing the total uplink energy efficiency of the system. Hence the optimal receiver filter coefficients are determined by solving the following optimization problem:

$$P_5 : \max_{\mathbf{u}_k} S_k(q_k, \mathbf{u}_k, \alpha), \quad (18a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } S_k(q_k, \mathbf{u}_k, \alpha) \geq S_k^{(r)}, \quad \forall k. \quad (18b)$$

Note that the satisfaction of constraints in (18b) will be ensured in the power allocation problem. Hence, we drop constraint (18b) and Problem P_5 can be reformulated as:

$$P_6 : \max_{\mathbf{u}_k} \quad (19)$$

$$\frac{N^2 \mathbf{u}_k^H (q_k \mathbf{\Gamma}_k \mathbf{\Gamma}_k^H) \mathbf{u}_k}{\mathbf{u}_k^H \left(N^2 \sum_{k' \neq k}^K q_{k'} |\phi_k^H \phi_{k'}|^2 \Delta_{kk'}^H \Delta_{kk'}^H + N \sum_{k'=1}^K q_{k'} \mathbf{D}_{kk'} + \frac{N}{\rho} \mathbf{R}_k \right) \mathbf{u}_k}.$$

Problem P_6 is a generalized eigenvalue problem [12], where the optimal solutions can be obtained by determining the generalized eigen vector of the matrix pair $\mathbf{A}_k = N^2 q_k \mathbf{\Gamma}_k \mathbf{\Gamma}_k^H$ and $\mathbf{B}_k = N^2 \sum_{k' \neq k}^K q_{k'} |\phi_k^H \phi_{k'}|^2 \Delta_{kk'}^H \Delta_{kk'}^H + N \sum_{k'=1}^K q_{k'} \mathbf{D}_{kk'} + \frac{N}{\rho} \mathbf{R}_k$ corresponding to the maximum generalized eigenvalue.

B. Power Allocation

In this subsection, we solve the power allocation problem for a given set of fixed receiver filter coefficients, $\mathbf{u}_k, \forall k$, and fixed values of quantization levels, $Q_m, \forall m$. The optimal transmit power can be determined by solving the following total energy efficiency maximization problem:

$$P_7 : \max_{q_k} S(q_k, \mathbf{u}_k, \alpha), \quad (20a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } S_k(q_k, \mathbf{u}_k, \alpha) \geq S_k^{(r)}, \forall k, 0 \leq q_k \leq p_{\max}^{(k)}, \forall k, \quad (20b)$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^K q_k \leq \nu \sum_{k=1}^K p_{\max}^{(k)}. \quad (20c)$$

As log is a monotonically increasing function, Problem P_7 is reformulated as follows:

$$P_8 : \min_{q_k, t_k} \prod_{k=1}^K (1 + t_k)^{-1} \quad (21a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } S_k(q_k, \mathbf{u}_k, \alpha) \geq S_k^{(r)}, \forall k, 0 \leq q_k \leq p_{\max}^{(k)}, \forall k, \quad (21b)$$

$$\text{SINR}_k \geq t_k, \forall k, \sum_{k=1}^K q_k \leq \nu \sum_{k=1}^K p_{\max}^{(k)}. \quad (21c)$$

where $t_k, \forall k$ refers to the slack variables. Problem (21) is a non-convex signomial problem. However, In Appendix B, we will show that all constraints in (21) can be reformulated into posynomial functions. Hence, if the objective function in (21a) is reformulated into a posynomial function, problem (21) is a standard GP. This motivates us to propose the following approach to transform Problem (21) into a standard GP. We use the SCA scheme proposed in [20] to approximate Problem (21) into a standard GP. Based on the analysis in [20], it is possible to search for a local optimum through solving a sequence of GPs which locally approximate the original optimization problem. This scheme is called the ‘‘inner approximation algorithm for non-convex problems’’ in [20]. This scheme provides an efficient solution for the original problem [19], [20]. Next, the following lemma using SCA is required [19, Lemma 1]:

Lemma 1. *Function $\Theta(x) = \kappa t^\xi$ can be used to approximate function $\Pi(x) = 1 + t$, near the point \hat{t} . The best monomial local approximation is obtained by the following parameters: $\xi = \frac{\hat{t}}{1+\hat{t}}$, $\kappa = \frac{1+\hat{t}}{\hat{t}^\xi}$, where $\Theta(t) \leq \Pi(t)$, $\forall t > 0$.*

Using the local approximation in Lemma 1, we can tackle the non-convexity of Problem P_8 , which enables us to reformulate Problem P_8 as follows:

$$P_9 : \min_{q_k, t_k} \prod_{k=1}^K t_k - \frac{\hat{t}_k}{1 + \hat{t}_k} \quad (22a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } S_k(q_k, \mathbf{u}_k, \alpha) \geq S_k^{(r)}, \forall k, 0 \leq q_k \leq p_{\max}^{(k)}, \forall k, \quad (22b)$$

$$\text{SINR}_k \geq t_k, \forall k, \sum_{k=1}^K q_k \leq \nu \sum_{k=1}^K p_{\max}^{(k)}, \quad (22c)$$

$$((1 - \delta)\hat{t}_k) \leq t_k \leq ((1 + \delta)\hat{t}_k), \forall k, \quad (22d)$$

where $\delta = 0.1$ and it controls the approximation accuracy [19].

Proposition 2. *Problem P_9 is formulated into a standard GP.*

Proof: Please refer to Appendix B. ■

Therefore, Problem P_9 is efficiently solved through existing convex optimization software. Based on these two sub-problems (P_6 and P_9), iterative Algorithm 1 has been developed by alternately solving both sub-problems, where we set $\epsilon_1 = \epsilon_2 = 0.01$.

VI. NUMERICAL RESULTS

A cell-free Massive MIMO system with M APs and K single-antenna users is considered in a $D \times D$ simulation area, where both APs and users are uniformly distributed at random. An uncorrelated shadowing model and a three-slope model for

Algorithm 1 Proposed algorithm to solve Problem P_4

1. Initialize $\mathbf{q}^{(0)}$, $\mathbf{U}^{(0)}$. Calculate the uplink $\text{SINR}_k^{(0)}$, $t_k^{(0)}$ and $S_k^{(r)}$ using $\mathbf{q}^{(0)}$ and $\mathbf{U}^{(0)}$, and set the initial SINR guess and initial auxiliary variables as $\hat{t}_k = \text{SINR}_k^{(0)}$, $\forall k$, and $t_k^{(0)} = \text{SINR}_k^{(0)}$, $\forall k$, respectively.
2. Set $\mathbf{q}^{(*)} = 0$, $t_k^{(*)} = t_k^{(0)}$, $\mathbf{U}^{(*)} = \mathbf{U}^{(0)}$, and $\tilde{E}_{e,k}^{(*)} = 0$, $\forall k$.
3. Calculate the constants ξ and κ using Lemma 1, and solve Problem P_9 with $t_k^{(*)}$ and $\mathbf{U}^{(*)}$, and find $\mathbf{q}^{(**)}$ and calculate $t_0^{(**)}$ and $t_k^{(**)}$.
4. If $|t_k^{(**)} - t_k^{(*)}| \leq 0.01$, then set $t_k^{(***)} = t_k^{(*)}$ and $\mathbf{q}^{(***)} = \mathbf{q}^{(*)}$ and go to step 8, otherwise, $t_k^{(*)} = t_k^{(**)}$ and go to step 3.
5. Solve Problem P_6 using $\mathbf{q}^{(*)}$ and calculate \mathbf{U} and set $\mathbf{U}^{(**)} = \mathbf{U}$.
6. Compute the objective value of Problem P_9 with $\mathbf{U}^{(**)}$ and $\mathbf{q}^{(*)}$ and call it $\tilde{E}_{e,k}^{(**)}$, $\forall k$.
7. If $|\tilde{E}_{e,k}^{(**)} - \tilde{E}_{e,k}^{(*)}| \leq 0.01$, $\forall k$, then $\mathbf{U}^{(*)} = \mathbf{U}^{(**)}$ and go to step 8, otherwise, go to step 3.
8. If the stopping criteria is satisfied terminate, otherwise, go to step 3.

Figure 1. The total energy efficiency of proposed Algorithm 1 versus number of iterations with $K = 20$, $M = 100$, $N = 1$, $\alpha = 2$, $\tau_p = 20$, and $D = 1$ km.

the path loss similar to [1] are considered. It is assumed that that \bar{p}_p and $\bar{\rho}$ denote the power of the pilot sequence and the uplink data powers, respectively, where $p_p = \frac{\bar{p}_p}{p_n}$ and $\rho = \frac{\bar{\rho}}{p_n}$, and we set $\bar{p}_p = 200$ mW and $\bar{\rho} = 1$ Watt, unless otherwise indicated. In addition, p_n refers to the noise power and we exploited the analysis in [1] to calculate it. Moreover, we use $\zeta = 0.3$, $P_U = 0.1$ Watt, $P_{\text{fix}} = 0.825$ Watt [27]–[30]. First, the convergence of the proposed Algorithm 1 is investigated. Fig. 1, presents the convergence of the proposed algorithm with $M = 100$, $K = 20$, $N = 1$, $\tau_p = 20$, and $\alpha = 2$. The figure confirms that the proposed Algorithm 1 converges in a few iterations. Fig. 2 presents the total energy efficiency of the proposed Algorithm 1 and the scheme with the equal power allocation with $M = 100$, $N = 1$, $\alpha = 2$, $\tau_p = 20$, and $D = 1$ km. As seen in Fig. 2, the proposed scheme significantly improves the total energy efficiency of cell-free Massive MIMO compared to equal power allocation scheme (i.e., $q_k = 1, \forall k, \mathbf{u}_k = [1, \dots, 1], \forall k$). In Fig. 3, we investigate the effect of number of quantization bits on the average energy efficiency performance of the system with orthogonal

Figure 2. Average energy efficiency versus number of APs with proposed Algorithm 1 and equal power allocation with $M = 100$, $N = 1$, $\alpha = 2$, $\tau_p = 20$, and $D = 1$ km.

Figure 3. The average energy efficiency of proposed Algorithm 1 versus number of quantization bits with $K = 20$, $N = 1$, $\tau_p = 20$, and $D = 1$ km.

Figure 4. The average energy efficiency of proposed Algorithm 1 versus the number of antennas per AP with $MN = 256$, $K = 40$, $P_{BT} = 10$ Watt, $C_{bh} = 100$ Mbps, and $\alpha = 4$ bits.

pilots, $P_{BT} = 1$ Watt and $D = 1$. By increasing number of quantization bits the spectral efficiency of the system increases, however, at the same time the required capacity of backhaul links increases which results in an optimum point in Fig. 3 which maximizes the energy efficiency of the system. In Fig. 4, we set $MN = 256$ as the total number of service antennas, and it can be seen for a fixed total number of service antennas, by reducing the total number of APs, M (which is equivalent to increasing number of antennas per APs, N), the total power consumption will decrease. On the other hand, reducing M results in throughput reduction. As a result, one

can find a trade off between M and N . Fig. 4 reveals the optimum values of M and N to have the highest total energy efficiency.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

We have considered cell-free Massive MIMO and analysed (using the Bussgang theorem) the scenario when a quantized version of the MRC weighted signals are available at the CPU. Per-user power constraints, backhaul capacity constraints and throughput requirements have been considered and an SCA has been exploited to convert the power allocation problem into a GP and efficiently solve the non-convex problem. Numerical results confirm that the proposed limited-backhaul system, while satisfying the optimization constraints, can achieve almost twice the uplink total energy efficiency compared to the case of equal power allocation. In addition, we examined the trade-off between the total number of APs and the number of antennas at the APs, for a given total number of antennas, and found that there is an optimal number of AP antennas which depends on the system parameters. Finally, the optimal number of quantization bits to maximize the uplink total energy efficiency has been determined.

APPENDIX A: PROOF OF THEOREM 1

The desired signal for the user k is given by

$$\text{DS}_k = \sqrt{\rho} \mathbb{E} \left\{ \sum_{m=1}^M u_{mk} \hat{\mathbf{g}}_{mk}^H \mathbf{g}_{mk} \sqrt{q_k} \right\} = N \sqrt{\rho q_k} \sum_{m=1}^M u_{mk} \gamma_{mk}. \quad (23)$$

The term $\mathbb{E}\{|\text{BU}_k|^2\}$ can be obtained as

$$\mathbb{E}\{|\text{BU}_k|^2\} = \rho \mathbb{E} \left\{ \left| \sum_{m=1}^M u_{mk} \hat{\mathbf{g}}_{mk}^H \mathbf{g}_{mk} \sqrt{q_k} \right|^2 \right\} = \rho N \sum_{m=1}^M q_k u_{mk}^2 \gamma_{mk} \beta_{mk}, \quad (24)$$

where the last equality comes from the analysis in [1]. The term $\mathbb{E}\{|\text{IUI}_{kk'}|^2\}$ is obtained as

$$\mathbb{E}\{|\text{IUI}_{kk'}|^2\} = \rho q_{k'} \mathbb{E} \left\{ \underbrace{\left| \sum_{m=1}^M c_{mk} u_{mk} \hat{\mathbf{g}}_{mk}^H \tilde{\mathbf{w}}_{mk} \right|^2}_A \right\} + \underbrace{\tau p_p \mathbb{E} \left\{ q_{k'} \left| \sum_{m=1}^M c_{mk} u_{mk} \left(\sum_{i=1}^K \mathbf{g}_{mi} \phi_k^H \phi_i \right)^H \mathbf{g}_{mk'} \right|^2 \right\}}_B. \quad (25)$$

Since $\tilde{\mathbf{w}}_{mk} = \phi_k^H \mathbf{W}_{p,m}$ is independent from the term g_{mk} similar to [1, Appendix A], the term A in (25) immediately is given by $A = N q_{k'} \sum_{m=1}^M c_{mk}^2 u_{mk}^2 \beta_{mk'}$. The term B in (25) can be obtained as

$$B = \underbrace{\tau p_p q_{k'} \mathbb{E} \left\{ \left| \sum_{m=1}^M c_{mk} u_{mk} \|\mathbf{g}_{mk'}\|^2 \phi_k^H \phi_k \right|^2 \right\}}_C + \underbrace{\tau p_p q_{k'} \mathbb{E} \left\{ \left| \sum_{m=1}^M c_{mk} u_{mk} \left(\sum_{i \neq k'}^K \mathbf{g}_{mi} \phi_k^H \phi_i \right)^H \mathbf{g}_{mk'} \right|^2 \right\}}_D. \quad (26)$$

The first term in (26) is given by

$$C = N \tau p_p q_{k'} \left| \phi_k^H \phi_{k'} \right|^2 \sum_{m=1}^M c_{mk}^2 u_{mk}^2 \beta_{mk'} + N^2 q_{k'} \left| \phi_k^H \phi_{k'} \right|^2 \left(\sum_{m=1}^M u_{mk} \gamma_{mk} \frac{\beta_{mk'}}{\beta_{mk}} \right)^2, \quad (27)$$

and

$$D = N \sqrt{\tau p_p} q_{k'} \sum_{m=1}^M u_{mk}^2 c_{mk} \beta_{mk'} \beta_{mk} - N q_{k'} \sum_{m=1}^M u_{mk}^2 c_{mk}^2 \beta_{mk'} - N \tau p_p q_{k'} \sum_{m=1}^M u_{mk}^2 c_{mk}^2 \beta_{mk'}^2 \left| \phi_k^H \phi_{k'} \right|^2. \quad (28)$$

Finally by substituting (27) and (28) into (26), and substituting (26) into (25), we obtain

$$\mathbb{E}\{|\text{IUI}_{kk'}|^2\} = N \rho q_{k'} \left(\sum_{m=1}^M u_{mk}^2 \beta_{mk'} \gamma_{mk} \right) + N^2 \rho q_{k'} \left| \phi_k^H \phi_{k'} \right|^2 \left(\sum_{m=1}^M u_{mk} \gamma_{mk} \frac{\beta_{mk'}}{\beta_{mk}} \right)^2. \quad (29)$$

The total noise for the user k is given by

$$\mathbb{E}\{|\text{IN}_k|^2\} = \mathbb{E} \left\{ \left| \sum_{m=1}^M u_{mk} \hat{\mathbf{g}}_{mk}^H \mathbf{n}_m \right|^2 \right\} = N \sum_{m=1}^M u_{mk}^2 \gamma_{mk}, \quad (30)$$

where the last equality is due to the fact that the terms $\hat{\mathbf{g}}_{mk}$ and \mathbf{n}_m are uncorrelated. The power of the quantization error for user k is given by

$$\mathbb{E}\{|\text{TQE}_k|^2\} = \mathbb{E} \left\{ \left| \sum_{m=1}^M u_{mk} n_{d,mk} \right|^2 \right\} = \sum_{m=1}^M u_{mk}^2 \mathbb{E}\{|n_{d,mk}|^2\}, \quad (31)$$

where the last equality is due to the fact that the elements of e_{mk} and u_{mk} are uncorrelated. Next, we use the following property of the quantization distortion power $\mathbb{E}\{|n_{d,mk}|^2\} = \sigma_{\hat{\mathbf{g}}_{mk}^H \mathbf{y}_m}^2 \mathbb{E}\{|\tilde{n}_{d,mk}|^2\}$. Defining $z_{mk} = \hat{\mathbf{g}}_{mk}^H \mathbf{y}_m$, we have

$$\sigma_{z_{mk}}^2 = \mathbb{E} \left\{ \left(\hat{\mathbf{g}}_{mk}^H \mathbf{y}_m \right)^H \left(\hat{\mathbf{g}}_{mk}^H \mathbf{y}_m \right) \right\} \quad (32)$$

$$\approx \rho \mathbb{E} \left\{ \left| \sum_{k'=1}^K u_{mk} \hat{\mathbf{g}}_{mk}^H \mathbf{g}_{mk'} \sqrt{q_{k'}} s_{k'} \right|^2 \right\} + \mathbb{E} \left\{ \left| u_{mk} \hat{\mathbf{g}}_{mk}^H \mathbf{n}_m \right|^2 \right\}.$$

For the second term of (32), we have $\mathbb{E}\{|\hat{\mathbf{g}}_{mk}^H \mathbf{n}_m|^2\} = N \gamma_{mk}$. The first term in (32) can be obtained as

$$\mathbb{E} \left\{ \left| \sum_{k'=1}^K u_{mk} \hat{\mathbf{g}}_{mk}^H \mathbf{g}_{mk'} \sqrt{q_{k'}} s_{k'} \right|^2 \right\} = \underbrace{\mathbb{E} \left\{ \left| \sum_{k'=1}^K u_{mk} \mathbf{g}_{mk}^H \mathbf{g}_{mk'} \sqrt{q_{k'}} s_{k'} \right|^2 \right\}}_I + \underbrace{\mathbb{E} \left\{ \left| \sum_{k'=1}^K u_{mk} \epsilon_{mk}^H \mathbf{g}_{mk'} \sqrt{q_{k'}} s_{k'} \right|^2 \right\}}_II, \quad (33)$$

where each element of ϵ is given by $\epsilon_{mk} = \mathcal{CN}(0, \beta_{mk} - \gamma_{mk})$. The terms I and II in (34) are given as follows: I = $N \beta_{mk} \sum_{k'=1}^K q_{k'} \beta_{mk'}$, and II = $N(\beta_{mk} - \gamma_{mk}) \sum_{k'=1}^K q_{k'} \beta_{mk'}$. Next, let us assume, using the Bussgang

decomposition, that we have $\mathbf{v}_k = \mathcal{Q}(\mathbf{z}_k) = a\mathbf{z}_k + \mathbf{d}_k^z$, where $\mathbf{z}_k = [z_{1k} \cdots z_{Mk}]$ and $z_{mk} = \hat{\mathbf{g}}_{mk}^H \mathbf{y}_m$, where z_{mk} is the input of the quantizer at the m th AP. In addition, $\mathbf{d}_k^z = [d_{1k}^z \cdots d_{Mk}^z]$, and a and \mathbf{d}_k^z are the Bussgang scalar factor and the quantization error, respectively, as defined in Subsection II-B. Based on the analysis in [32], we have

$$\mathbf{R}_{d_k^z d_k^z} \stackrel{(a)}{\approx} (b - a^2) \text{diag}(\mathbf{R}_{z_k z_k}), \quad (34)$$

where $\mathbf{R}_{d_k^z d_k^z}$ and $\mathbf{R}_{z_k z_k}$ refer to the covariance matrix of the quantization error and the covariance matrix of the input of the quantizer, respectively. Moreover, note that in step (a), we exploit the analysis in [32, Section V]. Thus, we have:

$$\mathbb{E} \left\{ \left| \sum_{m=1}^M u_{mk} d_{mk}^z \right|^2 \right\} \approx \sum_{m=1}^M u_{mk}^2 \mathbb{E} \left\{ |d_{mk}^z|^2 \right\}. \quad (35)$$

Finally, exploiting (32) and (35), we have

$$\mathbb{E}\{\text{TFQE}_k^2\} \approx N \underbrace{(b - a^2)}_{\sigma_{\tilde{\mathbf{z}}}^2} \sum_{m=1}^M u_{mk}^2 \left(\rho(2\beta_{mk} - \gamma_{mk}) \sum_{k'=1}^K q_{k'}/\beta_{mk'} + \gamma_{mk} \right). \quad (36)$$

By substituting (23), (25), (29) and (30) into (6), the corresponding spectral efficiency of the k th user is obtained by (7), which completes the proof of Theorem 1. ■

APPENDIX B: PROOF OF PROPOSITION 2

The standard form of GP is defined as follows [33]:

$$P_{\text{GP}} : \min f_0(\mathbf{x}), \quad (37a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } f_i(\mathbf{x}) \leq 1, i = 1, \dots, m, g_i(\mathbf{x}) = 1, i = 1, \dots, p, \quad (37b)$$

where f_0 and f_i are posynomial and g_i are monomial. Moreover, $\mathbf{x} = \{x_1, \dots, x_n\}$ is the optimization variables. The SINR constraint in (37) is not a posynomial function, however it can be rewritten into the following posynomial function:

$$\frac{\mathbf{u}_k^H \left(N^2 \sum_{k' \neq k}^K q_{k'} |\phi_k^H \phi_{k'}|^2 \Delta_{kk'} \Delta_{kk'}^H + N \sum_{k'=1}^K q_{k'} \mathbf{D}_{kk'} + \frac{N}{\rho} \mathbf{R}_k \right) \mathbf{u}_k}{\mathbf{u}_k^H (N^2 q_k \Gamma_k \Gamma_k^H) \mathbf{u}_k} \leq \frac{1}{t}, \quad \forall k. \quad (38)$$

By applying a simple transformation, (38) is equivalent to the following inequality:

$$q_k^{-1} \left(\sum_{k' \neq k}^K a_{kk'} q_{k'} + \sum_{k'=1}^K b_{kk'} q_{k'} + c_k \right) \leq \frac{1}{t}, \quad (39)$$

where $a_{kk'} = \frac{\mathbf{u}_k^H (\phi_k^H \phi_{k'}|^2 \Delta_{kk'} \Delta_{kk'}^H) \mathbf{u}_k}{\mathbf{u}_k^H (\Gamma_k \Gamma_k^H) \mathbf{u}_k}$, $b_{kk'} = \frac{\mathbf{u}_k^H \mathbf{D}_{kk'} \mathbf{u}_k}{\mathbf{u}_k^H (N \Gamma_k \Gamma_k^H) \mathbf{u}_k}$, $c_k = \frac{\mathbf{u}_k^H \mathbf{R}_k \mathbf{u}_k}{\mathbf{u}_k^H (\rho N \Gamma_k \Gamma_k^H) \mathbf{u}_k}$. The transformation in (39) shows that the left-hand side of (38) is a posynomial function. Similarly, it can be shown that the spectral efficiency constraint in (21b) can be transformed to a posynomial function. ■

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